

Building more trusted and reliable AI solutions to address the entire life cycle of industrial equipment

The researchers from the consortium of **AIDEAS** (AI Driven Industrial Equipment Product Life Cycle Boosting Agility, Sustainability and Resilience) are pleased to announce the launch of this ambitious R&D initiative granted by the European Commission under the Horizon Europe framework programme.

This project is funded with 6 million euros for **the development of artificial intelligence technologies to support the entire life cycle (design, manufacture, use, and repair/reuse/recycling) of industrial equipment** as a strategic tool to improve the sustainability, agility, and resilience of machinery manufacturing companies.

4 AI-based Suites for the 4 life cycle phases: Design, Manufacturing, Use, and Repair-Reuse-Recycle

AIDEAS will develop 4 artificial intelligence-based Suites covering the entire life cycle of industrial equipment:

1. **AIDEAS Industrial Equipment Design Suite:** artificial intelligence technologies, integrated with CAD/CAM/CAE systems, to optimise the design of structural components, mechanisms, and control components of industrial equipment.
2. **AIDEAS Industrial Equipment Manufacturing Suite:** Artificial intelligence technologies for the selection and procurement of industrial equipment components, optimisation of part manufacturing processes, sequencing of operations, quality control and customisation.
3. **AIDEAS Industrial Equipment Use Suite:** artificial intelligence technologies with added value for the user of industrial equipment, providing enhanced support for installation and initial calibration, production, quality assurance and predictive maintenance to work in optimal conditions.
4. **AIDEAS Industrial Equipment Repair-Reuse-Recycle Suite:** artificial intelligence technologies to extend the lifetime of machines through prescriptive maintenance (repair), facilitating a second life for machines through intelligent retrofitting (reuse) and identifying the most sustainable end-of-life (recycling).

AIDEAS Industrial Equipment Design Suite	AIDEAS Industrial Equipment Manufacturing Suite	AIDEAS Industrial Equipment Use Suite	AIDEAS Industrial Equipment Repair-Reuse-Recycle Suite
AIDEAS Machine Design Optimiser	AIDEAS Procurement Optimiser	AIDEAS Machine Calibrator	AIDEAS Prescriptive Maintenance
AIDEAS Machine Synthetic Data Generator	AIDEAS Fabrication Optimiser	AIDEAS Condition Evaluator	AIDEAS Smart Retrofitter
AIDEAS CAx Addon	AIDEAS Delivery Optimiser	AIDEAS Anomaly Detector	AIDEAS LCC/LCA/S-LCA
		AIDEAS Adaptive Controller	AIDEAS Disassembler
		AIDEAS Quality Assurance	

AIDEAS Machine Passport

The **AIDEAS** project consortium consists of **16 partners** from **8 European countries**, including prestigious Universities from Spain, Finland, Portugal, and Italy. The industrial partners are machinery manufacturers supplying industrial equipment to different industrial sectors: metal, stone, plastic, and food.

AIDEAS will show the performance, transferability, scalability, and capacity for large-scale deployment of the developed solutions through **demonstrations in real operating environments**; more specifically in four pilots that manufacture different types of machinery: Machining Centres, Cutting Machines, Blow Moulding Machines, and Inspection Machines.

The machinery industry in Europe is a foundation for employment, growth, and wealth, with some 3.2 million people employed. Industrial equipment is considered a key element for industrial development and the European Union has a historically strategic position in this sector. However, it is living on a technological edge in a very competitive landscape. It is, therefore, crucial to provide all EU stakeholders with AI technologies that ensure resilient design, deployment, and re-use of industrial equipment for increased global competitiveness and a reinforcement of its industrial strategic autonomy and resilience, and **AIDEAS** takes up the challenge.

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Learn more about AIDEAS:

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